

GENERAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE OFFICIAL BUSINESS STYLE OF THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

The article discusses the general characteristics of the official business style of the Russian language. In everyday business style, official correspondence between institutions and organizations, on the one hand, and private business papers, on the other, differ in content, genres and the nature of the language used. The language of legislative documents includes vocabulary and phraseology of state, civil, criminal law, labor codes, laws on marriage and family, etc.

There are quite a few definitions of the concept of style. If we compare these definitions, we can highlight the most general provisions: style is: 1) a type of literary language, 2) which functions (acts) in a certain sphere of social activity, 3) for which it uses the text structure and linguistic features specific to a given style means of expressing its content. In other words, styles are the main largest speech varieties. Style is realized in texts. You can determine the style and its features by analyzing a certain number of texts and finding common features in them.

INTRODUCTION

The purpose of this article is to briefly characterize the textual norms of official business style. The Russian literary language is a standardized and codified form of existence of the Russian language.

The typical structure of an official business text acts as a framework within which the writer specifies the text of the document - its linguistic content (the scope of language norms), and the extent of the writer's independence depends on what type of sample text the document belongs to. In each genre of a document, one can identify those details that carry constant information and involve a simple real "substitution": these are the names of the organization, the share of the person, the surname and initials of the writer, the title of the document, the signature, the date. We can fundamentally distinguish from them those details that carry a variable - specific information containing a statement of the essence of the case, and in other words, involve the work of the writer in formulating the circumstances, material and argumentation of the case. So, for an account, such a "free" detail is the motivation for the

amount to be paid; for a power of attorney - an accurate and comprehensive definition of the entrusted function; for a statement - the exact wording of the request or complaint and a brief argument.

A norm is an assessment by native speakers of certain facts as correct or incorrect, acceptable or unacceptable, appropriate or inappropriate.

The system of literary language norms is generally binding, codified (fixed). This system includes private norms: pronunciation; word usage; writing; shaping; correct; exemplary. At the same time, literary norms are perceived as mandatory.

For the concept of business style and the construction of a given text, it is necessary to have an idea of the functional styles (types) of the Russian language, since it performs a certain function in speech, which is determined by both linguistic factors, i.e., a set of stylistically significant linguistic means, as well as extralinguistic (non-linguistic) factors of communication.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A linguistic style is characterized by "a set of features, some of which are uniquely, in their own way, repeated in other styles, but a certain combination of which distinguishes one linguistic style from another." [5;14] Thus, the colloquial style is used in everyday speech, in conversation, in a relaxed atmosphere. In book speech the following are used: scientific style; journalistic style; business style; art style.

It should be noted that there is a close cohesion in the use of a particular style and situation of communication, type of thinking (logical-conceptual, cognitive-evaluative, informational, emotional), content of speech and purpose (communication of information, influence, etc.), which does not allow possibility of free choice of style. And the discrepancy between the style of the situation, the type of thinking, the content of speech and its purpose is therefore used in parodies.

All of the above indicates the relevance of studying the modern Russian literary language and its norms.

The official business style is very conservative, that is, it is quite resistant to the influence of time, which is explained by the legal situations developed by society, which are expressed in business documents.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Business style is a set of linguistic means, the function of which is to serve the sphere of official business relations, i.e. relations that arise between state bodies, between or within organizations, between organizations and individuals in the process of their production, economic, and legal activities. [4;216] The main form of implementation of business style is written.

The most important functions of this style - communication and influence - are implemented in such official documents as laws, regulations, decrees, orders, contracts, agreements, business correspondence, statements, receipts, etc. This style is also called administrative, since it serves the sphere of official, business relations, area of law and public policy.

This is the style of documents: international treaties, state acts, legal laws, regulations, charters, instructions, official correspondence, business papers, etc. Thus, the scope of

business speech can, in principle, be represented as a wide network of current official business situations and as a set of corresponding genres of documents. The relationship “official business situation - the corresponding genre of the document” means that the content of the document covers a variety of real business circumstances, corresponding not to a single circumstance, but to their whole type - a situation. As a result, the form and language of documents in an official business style appear to be standardized (corresponding to a single model), and the very requirement of standardization permeates the entire sphere of business speech.

Among language styles, the official business style stands out for its relative stability and isolation. Over time, it naturally undergoes some changes caused by the nature of the content itself. But many of its features, historically established genres, specific vocabulary, phraseology, and syntactic turns give it a generally conservative character. A typical feature of the official business style is the presence of numerous speech standards - clichés. [6;130-135] If in other styles stereotyped phrases often act as a stylistic flaw, then in an official business style in most cases they are perceived as a completely natural part of it.

Many types of business documents have generally accepted forms of presentation and arrangement of material. It is no coincidence that in business practice ready-made forms are used that only need to be filled out. Even envelopes are customarily labeled in a certain order (different in different countries, but firmly established in each of them), and this has its advantage for both writers and postal workers.

The above also determines the requirement of unambiguity, characteristic of business speech. This requirement predetermines the use of terms (close to unambiguous) of special language means in business speech; These are, for example: a decree, a resolution - in a clerical format, a plaintiff, a defendant - in a legal format, to testify to someone one's deep respect - in a diplomatic one. For the same reason, there is a typical desire not to use personal demonstrative pronouns he (she, it, they) in business texts, since their use in the context - if there is more than one noun of the same gender in it - may contradict the requirements for accuracy and clarity of presentation.

In general, despite the differences in content and variety of genres, the official business style is characterized by a number of common features: [4;219]

1. conciseness, compactness of presentation, “economical” use of language means;
2. standard arrangement of material, frequent obligatory form (identity card, various kinds of diplomas, birth and marriage certificates, monetary documents, etc.), the use of clichés inherent in this style;
3. widespread use of terminology, nomenclature names (legal, diplomatic, military, administrative, etc.), the presence of special vocabulary and phraseology (official, clerical), inclusion in the text of complex abbreviated words, in particular abbreviations;
4. frequent use of verbal nouns, denominate prepositions (based on, in relation to, in accordance with, in fact, by virtue of, for the purposes of, at the expense of, along the line, etc.), complex conjunctions (due to the fact that, due to the fact that, due to the fact that, due to the fact that, etc.), as well as stable phrases that serve to connect parts of a complex sentence (in case...; on the grounds that...; on the grounds that. ..; with the condition that...; in such a way that...; the fact that... etc.);

5. the narrative nature of the presentation, the use of nominative sentences with listing;
6. direct word order in a sentence as the predominant principle of its construction;
7. a tendency to use complex sentences that reflect the logical subordination of some facts to others;
8. almost complete absence of emotionally expressive speech means;
9. weak individualization of style.

The listed distinctive linguistic features of business style (stylistic, lexical, morphological, syntactic) organically fit into the written sphere of use of this style, into its characteristic genres of documentation.

The official business style, in the field of administrative-legal and administrative-economic activities, in legal proceedings, where reporting, documentation, and written speech takes place, is marked by a dual nature: it is characterized by concreteness of content and abstraction of means of expression. [5;15-16]

The lexical and phraseological units of the language have the color of an official business style. The vocabulary of official speech is characterized by the widespread use of thematically determined special words and terms (legal, diplomatic, military, accounting, sports, etc.). The lexical (dictionary) system of the official business style, in addition to general book and neutral words, includes:

1. linguistic clichés (clichés): raise a question, based on a decision, incoming and outgoing documents, assign control over execution, after the deadline;
2. professional terminology: arrears, alibi, black cash, shadow business;
3. archaisms: I certify this document.

In an official business style, the use of polysemantic words, as well as words with figurative meanings, is unacceptable, and synonyms are used extremely rarely.

In the official business style, from a number of synonyms, those that express the will of the legislator are selected: allow, prohibit, oblige, decree, indicate, appoint, etc. This determines the “properly prescriptive” nature of speech, designed in an official business style.

Business texts are distinguished by the use of words and expressions that are not accepted in other styles (the above, the following, the above, appropriate, prohibited, preventive measure, deed, punishable, etc.). These include stable phrases: cassation appeal, act of civil status, act of disobedience, recognizance not to leave, etc.). Regular use of such words and expressions, which do not have synonyms, contributes to the accuracy of speech and eliminates misinterpretations.

Official business speech reflects not individual, but social experience, as a result of which its vocabulary is extremely generalized. In the official document, preference is given to generic concepts, for example: arrive (instead of arriving, arriving, arriving, etc.), vehicle (instead of bus, plane, etc.), settlement (instead of village, city, village, etc.) etc.

In official speech, non-finite forms of verbs are more common - participles, gerunds, infinitives, which especially often act in the sense of the imperative mood (take note, make a proposal, recommend, withdraw from use, etc.). The present tense forms of the verb perform the function of a prescription: Enterprises are responsible for...; The tenant is responsible for the property (such verb tenses are called “present orders”).

The syntactic features of the official business style include:

1. the use of simple sentences with homogeneous members, and the rows of these homogeneous members can be very common (up to 8-10), for example: ... "fines as an administrative penalty can be established in accordance with the legislation of Russia for violation of safety and labor protection rules in industry, construction, transport and agriculture";
2. the presence of passive structures (payments are made at the specified time);
3. stringing the genitive case, i.e. use of a chain of nouns in the genitive case: results of the activities of the tax police...;
4. the predominance of complex sentences, especially complex sentences, with subordinate conditionals: If there is a dispute about the amount of amounts due to the dismissed employee, the administration is obliged to pay the compensation specified in this article if the dispute is resolved in favor of the employee.

The syntax of the official business style reflects the impersonal nature of speech (Complaints are submitted to the prosecutor; Transportation of goods is carried out). In this regard, passive constructions are widely used, which allow one to abstract from specific performers and focus on the actions themselves.

Syntactic constructions in official speech are saturated with clichéd phrases with denominate prepositions: in order to improve the structure; in connection with these complications; through cooperation and mutual assistance; based on the decision made. These syntactic clichés are a specific feature of the official business style. The use of such syntactic constructions is necessary to express typical situations. They make it easier and simpler to compile standard texts.

In official business documents, coordinating conjunctions are more common than subordinating ones (the law, the charter prescribes, but does not explain, proves). At the same time, a characteristic feature of business speech is the predominance of complex sentences: a simple sentence cannot reflect the sequence of facts to be considered in an official business plan.

Conditional infinitive constructions play a large role in the syntax of official business style (especially in the texts of laws, where this is motivated by the target task - to stipulate the conditionality of the legal norm). A characteristic feature of business speech is also the use of infinitive and impersonal sentences with the meaning of obligation.

CONCLUSION

Thus, the official business style is a style that serves the legal and administrative and public spheres of activity. It is used when writing documents, business papers and letters in government agencies, courts, as well as in various types of business oral communication.

The official business style is characterized by the absence of emotionally charged words, conciseness, and compactness of presentation. In official papers, the set of linguistic means used is predetermined. The most striking feature of the official business style is linguistic clichés, or so-called clichés; The more clichéd a document is, the more convenient it is to use.

The official business style has two varieties: the official documentary style and the everyday business style.

But, despite the differences in content and variety of genres, the official business style as a whole is characterized by common and important features:

1. completeness and accuracy of presentation, excluding the possibility of other interpretations;
2. clarity and specificity of wording, which is determined by the main function - to clearly inform about indisputable provisions and facts;
3. locale standard. These features find their expression: in the selection of linguistic means (lexical, morphological and syntactic); in the preparation of business documents.

Among the styles, the official business style stands out for its relative stability and isolation. Over time, it naturally undergoes some changes, but many of its features: historically established genres, specific vocabulary, morphology, syntactic phrases - give it a generally conservative character.

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